

MANAGEMENT OF POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME WITH AYURVEDIC MODALITIES - A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome is described as a syndrome manifested by amenorrhea, hirsutism and obesity associated with enlarged polycystic ovaries. ^[1] It is the most common endocrine disorder in a woman of reproductive age. ^[2] It is a metabolic, endocrine and lifestyle disorder. It is a multifactorial and polygenic condition. ^[3] Function of Hypothalamic-pituitary - ovarian axis is disturbed and causes hormonal imbalance. It is characterized by amenorrhea or oligomenorrhea, oligo or anovulation, obesity, hirsutism, acne, hyperandrogenism, hyperinsulinemia and further may cause infertility. Some of these features are similar to *Pushpaghni Jataharini* in *Ayurveda*. In present case study, a 21 yrs old female patient came to OPD of GACH, Dharashiv and diagnosed with PCOS. Aim of treatment is to reduce weight, restore normal hormonal function and to regulate the menstrual cycle. For this purpose, we basically focused on metabolic, endocrine and reproductive system and restored their normal functions. The treatment

modalities used here are *Nidanparivarjan*, *Deepan-Pachan*, *Shaman Chikitsa* and *Shodhan Chikitsa*. The *Shodhan Chikitsa* included *Yogbasti*. *Yogasana* plays significant role in weight reduction, stress reduction and normal hormonal function. Diet modification and lifestyle modification are very important in managing PCOS and to prevent recurrence of disease.

KEYWORDS - PCOS, Hyperandrogenism, Insulin resistance, *Pushpaghni Jataharini*, *Sanshaman Chikitsa*, *Yogbasti*.

INTRODUCTION

PCOS is basically a lifestyle disorder. It is contributed by factors such as poor eating habits, lack of exercise, stressful employment and surrounding environment. It results in weight gain and obesity. Obesity induces insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia which in turn increases the gonadal androgen production.^[4] Exact pathophysiology of PCOS is not clear. It includes some factors like Hypothalamic-pituitary compartment abnormality, Androgen excess and hirsutism, Anovulation, Obesity and insulin resistance.^[5]

Clinical features are increasing obesity (abdominal-50%), menstrual abnormalities (70%) in the form of oligomenorrhea, amenorrhea or dysfunctional uterine bleeding (DUB) and infertility. Presence of hirsutism and acne are the important features (70%). Acanthosis nigricans commonly affects nape of the neck, inner thighs, groin and axilla. HAIR-AN syndrome in patients with PCOS is characterized by hyperandrogenism, insulin resistance and acanthosis nigricans.^[6]

There is no direct reference of PCOS in *Ayurveda* but when we go through *Ayurvedic* literature there are some references which have similar signs and symptoms of PCOS. It can be correlated with *Artavkshay*.^[7,8] Also the clinical features of PCOS shows close resemble with *Pushpaghni Jataharini*.^[9] The woman have regular menstrual cycle but unable to conceive in *Pushpaghni Jataharini*. The other symptoms are obesity and excessive hair growth on cheeks. From reproductive point of view, the pathogenesis o PCOS is similar to *Nashtartava*.^[10] Vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha* causes *Avaran* of *Artav* leading to *Nashtartav*. To treat PCOS effectively, conventional methods often suggest making lifestyle changes like improving diet habits and adding exercise. Many studies have shown that regular physical activity can help improve insulin resistance and results in regular menstrual cycle.

CASE STUDY

A 21 years old married woman, resident of Alani, Dist. Dharashiv came to *Prasutitantra Evum Streeroga* OPD of GACH, Dharashiv on 20/01/2025 with chief complaints of Irregular menstrual cycle and weight gain since last 4 years. By looking at her previous USG report, it was found that the patient has bulky ovaries with PCOD and her follicular study was showing

anovulation. The investigations like haematology, urology and biochemistry analysis were within normal limit. TFTs and Prolactin level of the patient were normal. The patient was treated by allopathic treatment modalities in last 3 years and had taken OCP's for 3 months from July to October 2024. But after completion of OCP's cycle, the menstrual cycle again became irregular. So, the patient turns towards *Ayurvedic* treatment for proper cure of the disease.

Menstrual history

Age of menarche – 12 years

LMP – 23/10/2024

Cycle – Irregular

Interval – 60-90 days

Duration – 4-5 days

Amount – 2 pads/day

Bleeding contains clots with mild abdominal pain.

Marital History – married before 1.5 years

Obstetric History – Nulligravida

Medical History – No H/O HTN/DM/TB/BA/Thyroid disorder or any other major illness

Surgical History – No any surgical illness

Contraceptive History – Barrier method by husband

Personal History

Occupation – Housewife

Appetite – Good

Sleep – Good

Bowel – Clear

Bladder – Clear

Psychological status – Happy

Addiction – No smoking and alcohol

On Examination

GC – Fair

Temp – Afeb.

PR – 80/min

BP – 120/80 mmHg

Systemic Examination

RS – AEBE Clear

CVS – S₁S₂ Normal

CNS – cons, oriented

Breast Examination – Normal.

Per Abdominal Examination – Soft and non tender

Per Speculum Examination

- Cervix appears normal and healthy
- No any abnormal discharge seen
- No cervical ectopy seen
- No cystocele, No rectocele

Per Vaginal Examination

- Uterus - AVAF
- No cervical motion tenderness
- No vaginal fornices tenderness
- No any mass felt

Local Examination

- Acne – Present
- Acanthosis nigricans – Present
- Hirsutism - Present

Ashtavidha Parikshan

Nadi – Vatpradhan kapha

Mala – Samyak pravartan

Mutra – Samyak pravartan

Jivha – Sam

Shabd – Spasht

Sparsh – Anushnasheet

Druk – Prakrut

Akruti – Madhyam

USG Report (19/07/2024) – Before Treatment

Uterus AVAF of size 8.4 x 3.9 x 4.1 cm

Endometrial thickness – 10 mm

Rt. Ovary – 16cc

Lt. Ovary – 13cc

Both ovaries enlarged in size, shows multiple small follicles and increased stromal echogenicity, the follicles measure 5-8 mm and located along rim of ovary (Necklace sign)

F/S/O PCOD

UPT – Negative (20/01/2025)

Treatment modalities**1. Nidanparivarjan**

Nidan means causative factors of the disease. These factors should be omitted from daily routine. Patient was advised to avoid junk food like pizza, burger and all bakery products. Intake of products containing preservatives is minimized. Patient is also advised to avoid the sedentary lifestyle, *Divaswap* and avoid the stress with the help of *Pranayam* and meditation.

2. Oral medication (Deepan Pachan)

Medicine	Dose	Time	Duration
1. <i>Ampachak vati</i>	250 mg 2BD	Before meal	15 days
2. <i>Dashmool katutray kashay</i>	10 ml BD	Before meal	15 days
3. <i>Raktapachak kashay</i>	30 ml BD	Before meal	15 days

3. Sanshaman Chikitsa

Medicine	Dose	Time	Duration
1. <i>Lashunadi vati</i>	250 mg 2BD	Before meal	1 month
2. <i>Shatpushpa churn</i>	5 gm BD	After meal	3 months
3. <i>Maharasnadi kashay</i>	10 ml BD	Before meal	3 months
4. <i>Devdarvyarishta</i>	10 ml BD	After meal	1 month

4. Sanshodhan Chikitsa

3 cycles of *Yogbasti shodhan karma* done in this case.

<i>Yogbasti</i>	Duration
<i>Anuvasan basti</i> with <i>Sahacharadi tail</i> (60ml)	1 st cycle - 21/01/2025 to 28/01/2025
<i>Niruh basti</i> with <i>Erandsmuladi kashay</i> (650ml)	2 nd cycle - 18/02/2025 to 25/02/2025
	3 rd cycle - 19/03/2025 to 26/03/2025

5. *Yogasana*, Diet and Lifestyle modification

Yogasana plays an important role in maintaining harmony between body and mind and also significantly reduces obesity. Patient was advised to do 30 min *yogasana* daily including *Suryanamaskar*, *Dhanurasan*, *Bhujangasan*, *Ushtrasan*, *Chakrasan*. Daily 15 min *Pranayam* and Meditation is advised to relieve the stress. Food habits were improved. Sedentary lifestyle avoided. Sleeping during the day and waking up at late night is avoided.

Follow up and Outcomes

Deepan-Pachan and 1st cycle of *Yogbasti* completed and after 2 weeks patient had her menses on 14/02/2025. After menses 2nd cycle of *Yogbasti* completed and *Sanshaman Chikitsa* given. After that patient had her next menstrual cycle on 03/03/2025. Again 3rd cycle of *Yogbasti* conducted. Along with this *Ayurvedic* treatment, diet modification and exercise played an important role in weight loss. Patient was advised to do repeat ultrasonography and report reveals that the volume of both ovaries is significantly reduced. Patient regains her normal metabolic function. Hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis restored its normal function and there is normal production of reproductive hormones which ultimately results into normal menstruation. So, in this case integrated *Ayurvedic* approach and exercise helped patient to achieve her normal regular menstrual cycle.

Weight – Before treatment – 60 kg

– After treatment – 56 kg

BMI – Before treatment – 26.3

– After treatment – 25.1

USG Report (17/08/2025) – After treatment

Uterus AVAF of size 8.2 x 4.1 x 3.8 cm

Endometrial thickness – 6 mm

Rt. Ovary – 12.5cc

Lt. Ovary – 11.7cc

DISCUSSION

PCOS is a common endocrinopathy in woman of adolescent and reproductive age group which affects patient in many aspects of life and further leads to infertility. In this case,

patient had taken proper treatment, visited for each follow up, diet and exercise followed consciously. So, the patient got amazing results.

Deepan-Pachan drugs helped in balancing vitiated *Doshas* and restoring *Agni*, thereby improving the metabolism. *Sahacharadi tail*^[11] *anuvasan basti* through its *Sukshma*, *Vyavayi* and *Vikasi guna* enters the *Strotas* and removes the *Strotorodh*. It contains drugs having *Ushna virya* and *Kaphavata shamak* properties. *Erandmuladi niruh basti* maintains the functions of *Apana vayu* such as *Vatanuloman* and elimination of *Mala, Mutra* ad *Artav*. *Basti* given via rectal route absorbs through rectal mucosa and enters into systemic circulation. Entering into Gastrointestinal Tract (GIT), *Basti* stimulates Enteric Nervous System (ENS) and generates the stimulatory signals for Central Nervous System (CNS) as ENS resembles CNS.^[12,13] It results into regulation of Hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis. *Sanshaman Chitiksa* helped in balancing *Tridoshas* and reducing symptoms like acne, hirsutism and Acanthosis nigricans. Diet modification and exercise helped to reduce the weight.

CONCLUSION

In this case, polycystic appearance and ovarian volume reduced on ultrasonography. Normal hormonal function was restored. Clinically patient got relief from symptoms. Menstrual cycle became regular and there is improvement in menstrual interval, duration, amount and quality. Based on observations, it can be concluded that these *Ayurvedic* modalities altogether helps in relieving of symptoms and proved best cure for PCOS without any hazards.

Informed consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and associated clinical data.

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